

OVERVIEW OF FIGURATE NUMBERS

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Abstract:

Among the many several classes of numbers are used in mathematical idea, in particularly the figurate numbers are important role of understanding and how is connection between numbers and geometry. In this presentation I will discussed the few of, nature of figurate numbers.

Key Words: Figurate Numbers, Triangular Numbers, Square Numbers, Pentagonal Numbers And Hexagonal Numbers.

1. Introduction:

There are different way of communicating facts and ideas in mathematics. The figurate numbers are using the mathematical symbolic language and also used in geometric representation. There are two types of figurate numbers one called Plane figurate numbers or Two-dimensional figurate numbers and other type called Space figurate Numbers or Three-dimensional figurate numbers. A figurate number that can be shown by taking points or dots and arranging them into a regular shape. Figurate numbers can also form other polygons, no matter that shape, the number must create a regular polygon, the number that can be arranged that can be as a polygon made of dots, it is a figurate number. Figurate numbers may also be called polygonal numbers. The figurate numbers allows as to examine patterns and shape in numbers. In this presentation we will discussed basic of Triangular number, Square number and Pentagonal number.

2. Developing of Figurate Numbers:

The first invented of figurate number is the great mathematician and philosopher Pythagoras. Figurate numbers were a concern of Pythagorean worldview. Next the modern studied of figurate numbers goes to Pierre de Fermat, the important theorem of Fermat Polygon Number Theorem. Later, it become a significant topic for Euler, who gave an formula for all triangular numbers that are also a perfect square numbers, among many relating to figurate numbers he is discovered. Figurate numbers have played a significant role in modern recreational mathematics.

3. Triangular Number:

A numbers that assume at Triangular shape are called Triangular numbers. T_n denoted n^{th} Triangular number, then $T_n = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + (n - 1) + n = \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$.

There are some triangular numbers in the first 100 numbers.

These are 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, 28, 36, 45, 55, 66, 78, 91, ...

First few triangular numbers diagram are shown in below.

4. Square Number:

A square number is an integer and regular polygon. It is the product of some integer with itself. Another word saying, numbers that assume a square shape are called square numbers. The n^{th} square numbers are $n \times n = n^2$. The first few square numbers are 1, 4, 9, 16, 25, ...

First few square numbers diagram are shown in below.

5. Pentagonal Number:

A numbers that assume a pentagonal shape are called pentagonal numbers. And also says that pentagonal numbers are those enumerating a collection of objects which can be arranged in the form of a regular polygon. p_n is denoted by n th pentagonal number. The n th pentagonal numbers are $p_n = \frac{3n^2 - n}{2}$. The first few pentagonal numbers are 1, 5, 12, 22, 35, ...

First few pentagonal numbers diagram are shown in below.

6. Hexagonal Number:

Numbers that assume a hexagonal shape are called hexagonal numbers. A hexagonal number is a figurate number and also a regular polygon. The n th hexagonal number is denoted by h_n .

The formula of the n th hexagonal number $h_n = 2n^2 - n$. The first few hexagonal numbers are 1, 6, 15, 28, 45, ...

First few hexagonal numbers diagram are shown in below.

7. Conclusion:

In this presentation we are discussing of history of figurate numbers and how to way of developing in figurate numbers. A polygon number can be represented by points in a polygonal shape. The first number in the sequence is always 1, followed by the 3 points are triangular number, and 4 points as square number, 5 points as a pentagonal number, 6 points as a hexagonal number, this points are represented in regular polygon. The history of figurate numbers are very high and rich. But I will discussed in minimum of developing figurate numbers.

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